

Performance Evaluation of Content Based Image Retrieval Using Indexed Views

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Abstract : Digital information is expanding in exponential order in our life. Information that is residing online and offline are stored in huge repositories relating to every aspect of our lives. Getting the required information is a task of retrieval systems. Content based image retrieval (CBIR) is a retrieval system that retrieves the required information from repositories on the basis of the contents of the image. Time is a critical factor in retrieval system and using indexed views with CBIR system improves the time efficiency of retrieved results.

Keywords : content based image retrieval (CBIR), indexed view, color, image retrieval, cross correlation

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